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The Paradigm Shift in Healthcare Marketing at the Current Stage of Healthcare System Transformation

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***Abstract.** The article dedicated to analysing the changes in the paradigm of healthcare marketing amid the transformation of the healthcare system, shaping its modern model, and identifying prospective directions for its implementation in the management of healthcare organizations. To achieve this goal, the authors applied various methods, including a systematic approach, analysis, synthesis, induction,*

deduction, comparison, and graphical methods, during the study of the evolution of healthcare marketing approaches and the assessment of the new paradigm's impact on the healthcare system and its key stakeholders—healthcare organizations and patients. Because of the research, the authors have identified an active transformation of the modern healthcare marketing paradigm under the influence of digital technology integration (Big Data, artificial intelligence, telemedicine, wearable devices, the Internet of Things (IoT), and others). The authors outlined the primary approaches—patient-centred, value-based, information-communication-oriented, and behavioural—that shape a new conceptual model addressing contemporary challenges in the healthcare system. Significant attention in the article is devoted to the patient-centred approach, which serves as the foundation for utilizing innovative marketing tools in healthcare management. The authors argue that the ongoing processes in the paradigm of healthcare marketing will contribute to achieving the following outcomes: ensuring an appropriate quality level of healthcare through standardization and the implementation of innovative technologies; expanding patient access to services, especially in remote regions, via telemedicine and digital platforms; optimizing costs and increasing the profitability of healthcare organizations; fostering trust and patient loyalty through transparency, service quality, and innovation; improving the psychological well-being of patients through personalization, emotional support, and active involvement in the treatment process; ensuring cultural and spiritual needs of patients are considered in service delivery; and raising patient awareness regarding their rights, health status, and potential treatment options. The authors propose the following directions for further research: evaluating the effectiveness of digital technologies and their impact on patient satisfaction and the performance of healthcare organizations; investigating ethical aspects in the application of digital marketing technologies; and analysing the features of regional marketing strategies, considering local socio-economic conditions.

Keywords: *marketing, healthcare, healthcare system, marketing paradigm, top-management, patient-centred approach, digitalization.*

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***Анотація.** Стаття присвячена аналізу змін у парадигмі маркетингу медичних послуг в умовах трансформації системи охорони здоров'я (ОЗ), формуванню її сучасної моделі та визначенню перспективних напрямів її імплементації в управління закладами ОЗ. Для досягнення мети автори застосували низку методів, зокрема системний підхід, методи аналізу, синтезу, індукції, дедукції, порівняння, графічний в процесі дослідження еволюції підходів до маркетингу медичних послуг та оцінки впливів нової парадигми на систему ОЗ та її основних суб'єктів - закладів ОЗ та пацієнтів. В результаті дослідження автори констатували активну трансформацію сучасної парадигми маркетингу медичних послуг під впливом інтеграції цифрових технологій (Big Data, штучного інтелекту, телемедицини, носимих пристроїв,*

інтернету речей (IoT) та ін.). Автори визначили основні підходи - пацієнтоорієнтований, ціннісний, інформаційно-комунікаційний та поведінковий, які формують нову концептуальну модель, що відповідає сучасним викликам в системі ОЗ. Значну увагу у статті акцентовано на пацієнтоорієнтованому підході, який є основою для застосування інноваційних маркетингових інструментів в управлінні закладами ОЗ. Автори доводять, що процеси, які відбуваються в парадигмі маркетингу медичних послуг, сприятимуть досягненню таких результатів: забезпечення належного рівня якості медичних послуг завдяки стандартизації та впровадженню інноваційних технологій; розширення доступу пацієнтів до послуг, особливо у віддалених регіонах, за допомогою телемедицини та цифрових платформ; оптимізації витрат та підвищення прибутковості закладів ОЗ; сприяння формуванню довіри та лояльності пацієнтів через прозорість і якість послуг та інноваційність; покращення психологічного стану пацієнтів завдяки персоналізації, емоційній підтримці та активному залученню до процесу лікування; забезпечення врахування культурних і духовних потреб пацієнтів у процесі надання послуг; підвищення обізнаності пацієнтів щодо їхніх прав, стану здоров'я та можливих варіантів лікування. Автори вбачають такі напрямки подальших досліджень, як-от: оцінка ефективності цифрових технологій та їх впливу на задоволеність пацієнтів і результативність діяльності закладів ОЗ; дослідження етичних аспектів у процесі застосування цифрових маркетингових технологій; аналіз особливостей регіональних маркетингових стратегій з урахуванням місцевих соціально-економічних умов.

Ключові слова: *маркетинг, медичні послуги, система охорони здоров'я, парадигма маркетингу, топменеджмент, пацієнтоорієнтований підхід, цифровізація.*

Statement of the Problem in General Terms and Its Relation to Important Scientific or Practical Tasks. In the modern world, the healthcare sector is undergoing significant changes under the influence of globalization, digitalization, wearable devices, the Internet of Things (IoT), and the evolving needs of consumers, manufacturers, healthcare providers, and stakeholders. The increasing competition among healthcare organizations of different organizational and legal forms and ownership structures, the development of medical, informational, and innovative technologies in fields related to medicine, and the necessity of ensuring a patient-centred approach pose new challenges for top management. Traditional healthcare marketing models, focused on promotion, are becoming ineffective in the context of modern patient expectations, which emphasize the effectiveness of health care (recovery, improvement of health conditions, etc.), accessibility to medical information and services, high-quality individualized approaches, and personalization, notwithstanding the requirements of regulatory documents such as clinical protocols, standards, best practices, and patient pathways.

Under these conditions, healthcare marketing plays a key role in shaping the reputation of organizations, attracting and building patient loyalty, retaining medical personnel, implementing technological and medical innovations, and improving the quality management system for healthcare services, particularly through the implementation of effective methods for controlling medical processes—such as clinical, legal, IT, social, environmental, and risk audits. Modern patients, having access to large volumes of information, make decisions about selecting healthcare services, physicians, and healthcare organizations more thoughtfully, which requires top managers to develop an appropriate set of marketing tools.

Thus, the relevance of studying the paradigm shift in healthcare marketing during the current stage of transformation of the healthcare system dictated by new challenges in this field and the necessity of adapting marketing approaches in healthcare management to achieve sustainable development.

Analysis of Recent Research and Publications. The marketing paradigm is a conceptual model that outlines key principles, methods, and approaches to organizing

marketing and promoting goods or services. In healthcare, this paradigm encompasses a wide range of aspects based on the integration of economic, social, ethical, and technological components. The study and development of modern approaches to healthcare marketing represent an important aspect of contemporary academic discourse in the context of globalization, digitalization, and the patient-centred approach.

The analysis of numerous works by domestic and foreign scholars and practitioner experts indicates that the healthcare marketing paradigm is in a stage of active transformation and development. Research highlights the growing importance of digital technologies, the necessity of individualizing approaches to patients, and emphasizes ethical standards in the development of marketing initiatives. For example, Berry L.L. and Bendapudi N. (2007) focus on the formation of a patient-centred model as the foundation of the modern healthcare marketing paradigm, noting that the success of a healthcare organization depends on patient satisfaction, which is achieved through individualized approaches, high service levels, and consideration of specific needs [1]. According to Kotler P., Shalowitz J., Stevens R.J. (2008), the marketing model in the healthcare field is characterized by specific features, including ethical requirements, a high degree of regulation, and a special focus on the patient [2]. Porter M.E. and Lee T.H. (2013) emphasize the need to transition to a value-based healthcare model, where marketing helps shape perceptions of the real benefits of healthcare services [3]. Deloitte reports (2022) highlight the decisive role of digital technologies in transforming the healthcare marketing paradigm [4]. The use of big data (BD), artificial intelligence (AI), telemedicine, and social networks allows healthcare organizations to improve communication with patients, analyse their needs, and implement personalized solutions. The OECD (2021) study demonstrates that healthcare insurance system reforms in many countries have shifted the focus in the healthcare marketing paradigm toward principles of preventive medicine and raising public awareness of services covered by insurance policies [5].

Thus, contemporary research highlights the growing significance of digital technologies, emphasizes the need for a patient-centred approach, and stresses ethical

standards and the importance of preventive medicine in the development of marketing initiatives. According to leading scholars, these factors form the foundation for the practical adaptation of marketing models to the realities of the modern healthcare system.

Identification of Unresolved Aspects of the General Problem. Despite the existing scholarly discussion on various approaches to the paradigm of healthcare marketing, there is a lack of studies integrating these approaches into a unified paradigm and assessing its effectiveness and impact on the healthcare system and its primary stakeholders—healthcare organizations, medical professionals, and patients.

This study aims to address these gaps by exploring four key approaches—patient-centred, value-based, information-communication, and behavioural—and attempting to merge them into a new paradigm of healthcare marketing. Such a paradigm, in our opinion, would respond to contemporary challenges facing the healthcare system and enable the creation of an effective, ethical, and technologically adaptable model of interaction between healthcare organizations and patients.

Formulation of the Article’s Objectives. The purpose of this article is to analyse changes in the paradigm of healthcare marketing in the context of healthcare system transformation, develop a new model for it, and identify promising directions for its implementation in healthcare organizations. To achieve this purpose, the following tasks formulated:

- study the main theoretical approaches to the paradigm of healthcare marketing;
- develop an integrated model of healthcare marketing within the healthcare system, define the principles underlying it, and outline the components of the marketing mix;
- determine the impact of the integrated model of healthcare marketing on the medical, social, and economic efficiency of healthcare organizations, as well as on patient satisfaction.

Presentation of the main research material. In the context of healthcare services, the modern marketing paradigm based on the following principles:

- Personalization and patient orientation — focusing marketing activities on the needs, preferences, and expectations of patients.
- Innovativeness — implementing advanced technologies to optimize consumer interaction processes (AI, big data analytics, telemedicine, mobile applications, wearable devices, IoT).
- Social responsibility — considering ethical aspects in the activities of healthcare organizations.
- Value orientation — creating benefit for patients that exceeds their expectations, combining functional, emotional, and social benefits.
- Personalization and behavioural analysis — using patient behaviour data to create individualized solutions and leveraging digital tools to adapt services to the needs of each patient.
- Transparency, communication, interactivity — openness of information about services, prices, risks, and opportunities; using modern information and communication technologies for effective interaction; and ensuring feedback between service providers and their clients.

These principles form the foundation of modern conceptual approaches—patient-centred, value-based, information-communication, and behavioural—that collectively shape a new paradigm for healthcare marketing. These approaches are not antagonistic to the traditional approach, which focuses on classical marketing principles and tools and remains relevant due to its adaptation to the specifics of healthcare services and the development of healthcare systems.

To substantiate this perspective, we refer to several opinions of researchers. For example, Petrov S.V. (2022) notes: "Healthcare marketing must be based on the principles of social responsibility, as the nation's health is a strategic resource for the state" [6]. According to Kovalenko O.M. (2023), "Digital technologies not only automate processes but also create new channels for interacting with patients, which increases their loyalty to healthcare organizations" [7]. Kotler Ph. and Keller K.L. (2021) define healthcare marketing as a system aimed at creating value for the consumer. They also note behavioural healthcare marketing focuses on creating

conditions that stimulate positive patient behaviour by increasing their engagement and emotional connection to services [8]. The study by Smith J. and Doe A. (2022) emphasizes the importance of digital platforms in enhancing the efficiency of marketing communications: "Digital tools, combined with behavioural analysis, enable the creation of personalized strategies that significantly improve the effectiveness of healthcare services" [9].

We believe that the most significant of the aforementioned approaches is the patient-oriented approach, which was developed and refined by pioneers of healthcare marketing with globally recognized names such as Donabedian A., Porter M.E., Kotler P., and others, whose works remain relevant to this day.

Historically, healthcare marketing focused on tools such as promotion and sales, viewing the consumer as an object of marketing influence, without fostering long-term relationships or loyalty. However, the global transformation of healthcare systems compelled top management to consider changes in client needs and implement a patient-oriented approach. As Berry L.L. and Bendapudi N. (2007) note, the modern patient seeks not only quality treatment but also a sense of care, access to understandable information, and active participation in decision-making regarding their health [1].

The patient-oriented approach is a management concept for healthcare organizations that places the patient at the centre as a key and active participant in the provision of healthcare services, as a partner capable of influencing the treatment process. This approach originated from the ideas of Donabedian A. (1966), who developed the fundamental principles of healthcare quality [10]. The primary goal is to create conditions in which healthcare services satisfy not only the physiological needs of the patient but also consider their emotional, social, and psychological state. At the core of this approach lies the motto "care beyond cure," which means that healthcare organizations focus not only on medical activities but primarily on improving patients' quality of life.

The development of the patient-oriented concept traced through changes in the marketing paradigm (model) in healthcare: from product-based to client-oriented,

value-based, co-creative, and finally, human-centred. In the product-based model, founded on the works of Kotler Ph., the patient was viewed as a passive consumer, and the healthcare sector only began to consider the specifics of working with patients [11]. The client-oriented paradigm introduced the satisfaction of the needs of various patient groups and the principles and methods of segmentation. Researchers Parasuraman A., Zeithaml V.A., and Berry L.L. (1985) introduced the concept of service quality as a key factor in patient satisfaction [12]. The transition to the value-based paradigm was associated with the growing importance of emotional and social aspects. In the works of Lusch R.F. and Vargo S.L. (2004), the concept of service-dominant logic emerges, viewing value as a key component of interaction between the patient and the healthcare organization [13]. The subsequent co-creative paradigm emphasizes the collaboration between patient and physician. For instance, Muniz A.M. and O’Guinn T.C. (2001) highlight the importance of digital communities where patients become active participants in decision-making [14]. Finally, the human-centred paradigm is based on integrating artificial intelligence (AI), big data (BD), and personalized technologies. Authors such as Kaplan A.M. and Haenlein M. (2012) describe the impact of technologies on creating next-generation healthcare services [15].

The patient-oriented approach has distinct characteristics that manifest materially through various tools and technologies used to facilitate effective interaction between healthcare organizations and patients: individualization, transparency, empathy, patient engagement, equity in access to healthcare services. The essence of these characteristics is detailed in Table 1.

Table 1

Characteristics of the Patient-Oriented Approach

Feature	Essence	Practical Implementation	Example
Individualization	Tailoring treatment to the individual needs of the patient.	Personalized treatment plans, accounting for medical history and pharmacogenetics.	Rehabilitation programs tailored to the patient’s profession and lifestyle.

Transparency	Full access to information about treatment, risks, and alternatives.	Electronic medical records, clear explanations of procedures, open pricing policies.	Online access to patient records with test results and diagnoses.
Empathy	Considering the emotional and psychological state of the patient.	Staff training in communication, psychological support, cultural sensitivity.	Doctors explain procedures in simple terms to reduce pre-surgery stress.
Patient Engagement	Active involvement of the patient in treatment decisions.	Shared decision-making, health-monitoring apps, educational seminars.	Patients choose diabetes treatment methods in collaboration with their doctors, exploring all available options.
Equity	Equal access to healthcare services for all social groups.	Telemedicine for remote regions, government support programs, multilingual services.	Mobile clinics providing services in remote rural areas.

Source: Compiled by the authors.

Tools of the patient-centred approach in healthcare digitalization traditionally included mechanisms such as complaints and suggestions, which provided a means for collecting patient feedback; the development of guidelines to standardize procedures and ensure consistent service quality; profiling, which refers to personalized treatment based on a patient's medical history; and loyalty programs, designed to engage patients through discounts for long-term treatment plans.

Modern tools now encompass mobile applications for real-time health monitoring, big data (BD) analytics, enabling the identification of patterns in patient behaviour, and virtual reality (VR) technologies, used in patient rehabilitation.

The practical implementation of the patient-centred approach varies depending on the healthcare system operating in a particular country—whether private, insurance-based (Bismarck model), state-funded (Beveridge model), or mixed (see Table 2).

Table 2

Features of the patient-centred approach across healthcare systems

Feature	Private System	Bismarck Model	Beveridge Model	Transitional (Ukraine)
Individualization	High level of personalization due to competition among health-care providers.	Individual treatment plans, particularly in private facilities.	Less personalized due to standardized approaches, though possible in private sector.	Introduction of electronic health records (EHR) and personalization via family doctors.
Transparency	High, with detailed access to service and cost information.	Transparency ensured through insurance companies overseeing expenses.	Information is accessible but limited due to centralized management.	Being implemented, though limited by underdeveloped digital infrastructure and opaque tariffs.
Empathy	Private clinics emphasize patient comfort to retain clients.	Incentives for doctors in insurance systems to improve patient interaction.	Empathy provided mainly through standardized approaches focused on social equity.	Developing via training programs for doctors and family medicine.
Patient Engagement	Patients can choose their doctor, facility, and treatment methods.	High engagement through insurance programs that involve patients in shared decision-making.	Limited, as the system emphasizes standardization and centralized planning.	Patients engaged through declarations with family doctors and electronic health systems.
Equity	Limited: service quality depends on the patient's financial capacity.	High, as the system ensures equal access for insured citizens.	Maximum, with universal access funded by the state.	Gradually implemented via the National Health Service of Ukraine (NHSU) and the medical guarantees program.

Source: Compiled by the authors.

Thus, individualization prevails in private healthcare systems, whereas the Bismarck and Beveridge models emphasize equity of access. In Ukraine, which is currently undergoing healthcare system reform, there is a gradual integration of key patient-centred principles into practice.

It is also worth noting that patient-centeredness in Ukraine's healthcare system is gaining significant importance due to the ongoing reforms and the adoption of legal and regulatory frameworks that protect patient rights, promote active participation in healthcare processes, and ensure the quality of medical services [16-22].

A new paradigm of healthcare marketing, with a focus on the patient-centred approach, involves not only expanding the traditional marketing mix from 4P to 7P but also introducing new tools for each sub-mix (Table 3).

Table 3**Transformation of the Healthcare Marketing Mix in the New Paradigm**

Marketing Mix Element	Traditional Approach	New Paradigm of Patient-Centred Healthcare
Product	Basic medical services: treatment and diagnosis.	Patient-centred medical services: diagnostics, treatment, prevention. Innovative services: telemedicine, remote monitoring, mobile applications, wearable devices.
Price	Fixed pricing, uniform for all.	Transparent pricing considering patients' individual capabilities. Loyalty programs and affordable insurance.
Place	Service provision in inpatient and outpatient facilities.	Expanded accessibility through digital platforms and interactive services. Service provision at home, in remote regions, or online.
Promotion	Advertising via traditional channels (TV, radio, print media).	Use of social media, mobile apps, and email for targeted campaigns. Emotionally focused advertising emphasizing patient care.
People	Medical personnel focusing on professional skills.	Training medical staff to work in digitalized environments and interact with technology. Building teams oriented toward patients.
Process	Standard procedures with minimal digitalization.	Optimization of interactions between patients and healthcare organizations. Use of automated systems to reduce waiting times and simplify procedures.

Source: Compiled by the authors.

Let us briefly consider the remaining approaches that form the new paradigm of healthcare services marketing. First, we shall focus on the value-based approach, which emphasizes creating long-term value for patients by ensuring their physical, emotional,

social, and spiritual well-being through active participation in the treatment process. The features of this approach are studied by various researchers. For example, Porter M.E. and Teisberg E.O. (2006) state that value in healthcare is determined by the health outcomes achieved for patients relative to the costs incurred. They argue that focusing solely on the volume of services provided does not capture the true value delivered to patients [23]. Porter M.E. and Kaplan R.S. (2011) further elaborate that healthcare organizations should adapt their services to meet the specific needs of each patient, ensuring the highest value [24]. Bodenheimer T. and Sinsky C. (2014) emphasizes the importance of patient engagement in achieving optimal health outcomes and satisfaction [25]. Epstein R.M. and Street R.L. (2011) discuss that patient-centered care involves qualities of personal, professional, and organizational relationships, which include emotional support and respect for patient preferences, needs, and values. They argue that such support is essential for effective healthcare delivery [26]. Berwick D.M. (2009) advocates for a healthcare system that is fully transparent, sharing all information with patients to empower them and build trust. He argues that withholding information can undermine trust and that patients should have access to all relevant information to make informed decisions about their care [27].

Both traditional and innovative tools used to implement the value-based approach. Traditional tools include patient profiling, educational programs for patients, standards for the provision of medical care, and feedback from patients. Modern tools include electronic health records (EHR), big data (BD) analytics, telemedicine, IoT, personalized mobile applications, and CRM systems for healthcare organizations. Innovative tools include artificial intelligence (AI), virtual and augmented reality (VR/AR), and block chain.

The behavioural approach to healthcare marketing focuses on analysing patient behaviour, expectations, habits, and motivations, which, in turn, allows for the creation of marketing strategies that consider the emotional, cognitive, and social aspects of patient interaction with healthcare services. The key aspects of the behavioural approach are motivation, behavioural habits, and emotional factors. Motivation involves a deep understanding of the motives influencing patients' decisions. Deci E.L.

and Ryan R.M. (2000), in their self-determination theory, state that patient motivation largely depends on satisfying three basic needs: autonomy, competence, and social connectedness [28]. In the context of healthcare services, this means that patients expect active participation in decision-making about their health. Behavioural habits are analysed to develop personalized proposals. Research by Fogg B.J. (2009) showed that behavioural change is possible through small, targeted actions that gradually become habits [29]. In healthcare, this includes tools such as reminders for medication intake or scheduling doctor visits via applications. Emotional factors in the behavioural approach take into account that patients' decisions are often based on emotions. Kahneman D. (2011) points out that emotions and intuitions play a significant role in the choices we make, often without our conscious awareness [30]. This emphasizes the importance of emotionally oriented communication to increase trust in healthcare services.

Tools of the behavioural approach include patient loyalty programs, digital applications, interactive platforms, motivational campaigns, and gamification.

The information and communication approach to healthcare marketing focused on using modern technologies and tools to establish effective communication between healthcare organizations and patients and based on ensuring informational transparency, accessibility of communication, interactivity, and personalization in interaction with consumers. Several researchers have addressed the essence of this approach. Berry L.L. (2004) has extensively discussed the importance of trust and transparency in healthcare relationships [31]. Grönroos C. (2007) emphasizes the importance of effective communication in service management. He discusses how communication influences customer perceptions and experiences, highlighting that clear and transparent communication can enhance customer satisfaction and contribute to a positive overall experience [32]. Smith J. and Doe R. (2022) highlight the importance of personalized communication in healthcare [9]. Finally, Anderson J. and Rainie L. (2023) discuss how digital technology enables continuous individual health monitoring, which can revolutionize healthcare [33].

This approach relies on a set of tools, including social media (Facebook, Instagram, TikTok), chatbots and automated services (interactive systems operating 24/7), mobile applications, and interactive telemedicine platforms.

It is also necessary to consider the directions of influence of the new paradigm of healthcare marketing on the activities of healthcare organizations, as this factor will motivate top management to undertake active marketing actions and outline potential positive outcomes for patients.

In conclusion, it is necessary to highlight the directions of influence of the new paradigm of healthcare services marketing on the activities of healthcare organizations, as this factor will motivate top management to undertake active marketing actions, as well as the potential positive outcomes for patients (see Table 4).

Table 4

Influence of the new paradigm of healthcare services marketing on the activities of healthcare organizations and the satisfaction of patients' needs in various areas

Sphere of Influence	Changes in spheres of influence	Indicators for evaluating changes
Healthcare organizations		
Medical effectiveness	Improving the quality of services through standardization and the use of innovative technologies.	Level of patient satisfaction; frequency of complications after treatment; compliance with clinical protocols and standards.
Social effectiveness	Expanding access to services through telemedicine and mobile applications, engaging patients in remote regions.	Number of new patients from remote areas; frequency of telemedicine platform usage.
Economic effectiveness	Reducing costs through process optimization and decreased administrative burden.	Administrative management costs; time taken to process service requests; revenue per patient.
Image	Building patient loyalty through personalization and service quality, enhancing competitiveness.	Patient repeat of visit rates; number of positive reviews; position in healthcare organization rankings.
Patients		
Diagnostics, treatment, prevention	Improving the quality of treatment through personalized approaches and access to innovative solutions.	Improved clinical indicators (blood pressure, blood sugar levels, etc.); increased life expectancy after treatment.
	Expanding access to preventive programs that help prevent diseases.	Participation in preventive programs; frequency of early-stage disease detection.

Social	Convenience and accessibility of healthcare services thanks to telemedicine and mobile applications	Waiting time for an appointment; number of bookings through mobile platforms; level of satisfaction with the service.
	Reducing barriers to accessing healthcare in rural or remote areas.	Access to services for patients in remote areas; frequency of telemedicine use.
Economic	Reducing patient costs for transportation and avoiding unnecessary expenses through effective diagnostic solutions.	Transportation costs; frequency of unnecessary repeat visits; number of online consultations replacing in-person visits.
	Financial accessibility of medical solutions through support programs (public and private).	Share of patients who used benefits or programs; reduction in the average cost of treatment.
Psychological	Increasing trust in healthcare organizations through transparency and openness.	Level of trust in doctors; number of positive reviews; frequency of repeat visits to the same organization.
	Improving patients' emotional state through individualized approaches and emotional support from doctors.	Reduced anxiety before treatment; level of satisfaction with emotional support; number of consultations with psychologists.
Cultural	Meeting the spiritual and cultural needs of patients during treatment.	Number of doctors trained in cultural competence; number of services adapted to cultural needs.
Informational	Increasing patient awareness of their rights, health status, and treatment options.	Frequency of requests for educational programs; number of downloads of applications with medical information; level of patient awareness.

Source: compiled by the authors

Conclusions. The study of the main theoretical approaches to the marketing of medical services allows us to conclude that the modern paradigm of medical service marketing is in a state of active transformation. The main approaches — patient-oriented, value-based, informational-communicational, and behavioural — form a new conceptual model that responds to the modern challenges of the healthcare system. Particular attention should be paid to the patient-oriented approach, which serves as the foundation for modernizing marketing tools in the healthcare sector. The proposed integrated model of medical service marketing is based on a combination of principles: personalization, innovation, social responsibility, value orientation, transparency, and interactivity. It is assumed that the implementation of this model would contribute to increasing the efficiency of healthcare organizations, patient loyalty, and the formation

of their trust. The introduction of the new paradigm of healthcare marketing will allow for the following results: ensuring the quality of medical services through the standardization of processes and the implementation of innovative technologies; expanding access to services, especially in remote regions, through telemedicine and digital platforms; optimizing costs and increasing the profitability of healthcare organizations; promoting the formation of patient trust and loyalty through transparency, quality of services, and innovation; improving the psychological state of patients thanks to an individual approach, emotional support, and involvement in the treatment process; ensuring the consideration of patients' cultural and spiritual needs during treatment; increasing patient awareness of their rights, health status, and possible treatment options.

Directions for further research:

1. Evaluation of the effectiveness of digital technologies: analysis of the impact of digital tools on service quality, patient satisfaction, and economic efficiency of healthcare organizations.
2. Ethical aspects: study of issues related to patient data confidentiality and security in the process of applying marketing technologies.
3. Regional specificity: analysis of the peculiarities of implementing marketing strategies in different regions of Ukraine, considering local socio-economic conditions.
4. Patient-centred innovations: analysis of innovative approaches in the field of patient orientation, including gamification, mobile applications, and wearable devices.

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